

A PERSONALLY-CENTERED APPROACH TO TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

САЙЛАУБЕКОВА З.Ж., ЕРФАЛИ А.Е., НУРУМ З.Р., НУРЛАН Н.Н.

Магистранты ВКУ имени С. Аманжолова

Научный руководитель к.ф.н., профессор кафедры иностранных языков и переводческого дела ВКУ имени С. Аманжолова: **ФЕДОСОВА С.А.**

Abstract: *Importantly, this approach aims to enable each student to embody their own individuality, with the help of the teacher and their own efforts. The essence of a student-centered approach lies in meeting the needs and interests of the child, developing their unique personality, and not merely conforming their development and formation to established state or societal standards.*

Keywords: *individuality, student-centered approach, professional interests, foreign languages, students, mediocre, frameworks, thinking.*

Personality... is what a person makes of themselves, affirming their human life.

Alexey Leontyev

A person exists only to the extent that they realize themselves. They are, therefore, nothing other than the sum of their actions, nothing other than their own life. Jean-Paul Sartre

Considering the concept of a "student-centered approach" and its essence, it should be noted that this approach to teaching takes into account the age, psychological, and professional interests, capabilities, and needs of students, relying on the principles of differentiation and individualization of learning, and fostering their personal development. Crucially, this approach aims to ensure that each student embodies their own individuality, with the support of the teacher and their own efforts. The essence of a student-centered approach lies in satisfying the needs and interests of the child, fostering their unique personality, and not merely conforming their development and development to established state or societal standards. In the age of modern technology and progressive discoveries, there is a pressing need to study various fields of science, where knowledge of foreign languages is far from unimportant. One of these sought-after universal languages of communication among people around the world is English. It is impossible for a future English teacher not to be interested in current events. The challenge of our profession is to teach the younger generation a foreign language correctly and competently, without forcing students into a mediocre framework of thinking.

Now let's explore the connection between this approach, foreign language teaching, and middle school students.

Every nationality has its own unique characteristics, and Americans and the British are no exception. You might wonder why Americans and the British? Because these are two nations for whom English is rightfully considered their native language. Americans are distinguished by a unique flexibility in their perception and assessment of what is happening around them. On the one hand, they quickly assess practical situations and navigate their surroundings with relative ease. A passion for improvement and invention is a characteristic feature of the American way of life. As a counterpoint to American culture, one can imagine the culture of the British. The British, on the other hand, find it difficult to get along with others, but their friendships are stronger and more enduring; they have a great need for recognition and respect from others. Based on this, we can conclude that a student-centered approach to learning English is the most optimal option, as communicating with representatives of the aforementioned cultures on a more or less equal basis requires the development of independent, capable individuals in our environment. Observing several representatives of American culture from a distance, we can confidently say that they value creative, thinking individuals with clearly defined priorities and principles, who hold their own opinions. It's not surprising that they teach their students to think and reason in a way that allows everyone to be heard

and have the right to their own point of view. In our opinion, this is the most illustrative example of the use of a student-centered approach in the educational process.

We specifically studied the student-centered approach with middle school students, as at this age, it is necessary to support students in the next phase of developing their worldview, views, personal priorities, etc. Typically, these are boys aged 10-15. This age group is called "adolescence," which implies a conscious regulation of one's actions, the ability to consider the feelings and interests of others, and to orient one's behavior toward them. During this, the shortest period in astronomical time, a teenager undergoes a great developmental journey: through internal conflicts with oneself and others, through external breakdowns and ascents, they can gain a sense of individuality. However, society, which is opening up to their consciousness, cruelly initiates this. The cause of psychological difficulties is associated with puberty, an uneven development in various areas. This age is characterized by emotional instability and sharp mood swings (from exaltation to depression). The most violent affective reactions arise when someone around them attempts to hurt the teenager's pride. During this period, diametrically opposed needs and traits coexist within the adolescent's personality. Today, a teenage girl sits modestly with her relatives and discusses virtue. But tomorrow, with war paint on her face and a dozen earrings pierced in her ear, she'll go to a nightclub, declaring that "you have to experience everything in life." But nothing special (from the child's perspective) has happened: she's simply changed her mind. As a rule, teenagers focus their mental activity on the area that most fascinates them. However, interests are fickle. After a month of swimming, a teenager will suddenly declare themselves a pacifist, and that killing anyone is a terrible sin. And therefore, they'll take up computer games with the same passion. Therefore, we focus on the age of the students, as this will be the starting point for a student-centered approach to foreign language teaching.

Theme: «What do you think about your future? »

After all, to successfully learn a foreign language, one must be passionate and interested in the practical application of the acquired knowledge.

This implies that a student-centered approach is ideally suited for teaching not only school subjects but also foreign languages.

Before moving on to the practical part, I would like to explain the forms of student-centered foreign language teaching in general. As part of the integration of student-centered education and information technology, it is becoming necessary to use the following forms in English lessons: individual work; group work; differentiated work, creative tasks of one's own choosing; independent work; collaboration training; project-based learning; multi-level learning; and creating a situation of success. Below are detailed examples of the application of the above forms of student-centered approach for middle school students.

Example 1. Group work on the proposed topics.

Make up groups of four.

1. Healthy food
2. Fast food

The task is to discuss the given topics in groups. However, the first group will prove that healthy food is very useful and the second group against say that fast food is more useful than healthy. On a blackboard, you can find keywords you should use in speech. You have 10 minutes for discussion.

Keywords: keep fit, balance, strong health, vitamins, to go in sports, gym, to get, process, getting better, milk shakes, crispy, fat, tasty, depend on, flavor, to make, restaurants, fast, to save time, cheap, price.

Example 2. Differentiated work using cards.

«FINE» STAGE – 2 mistakes and max. mark is 4.
«GOOD» STAGE – 1 mistakes and max. mark is 4.
«HAPPY» STAGE – no mistakes and mark is 5.

«Fine» stage:

- Make up 6 sentences using Future Simple and Present Simple Tenses. Use keywords: space discoveries, to be optimistic about, they say...to control, diseases, enter competition, be nervous (exited), get through to the final, deadline, free, left to, moved to, biographies.

«Good» stage:

- Make up 6 sentences using Future Simple and Present Simple Tenses and then retell your opinion. Use keywords: space discoveries, to be optimistic about, they say...to control, diseases, enter competition, be nervous (exited), get through to the final, deadline, free, left to, moved to, biographies.

Example: Creating a Situation.

Students are presented with a situation titled "How to Survive on an Uninhabited Island?"

«FINE» STAGE – 2 mistakes and max. mark is 4.
«GOOD» STAGE – 1 mistakes and max. mark is 4.
«HAPPY» STAGE – no mistakes and mark is 5.

«Happy» stage:

- Make up a dialogue about our future lifestyle using Future Simple and Present Simple Tenses. The number of sentences are about 16. Use keywords: space discoveries, to be optimistic about, they say...to control; diseases, enter competition, be nervous (exited), get through to the final, deadline, free, left to, moved to, biographies, Government, population, Earth, the Sun,

To ensure a more correct flow of reasoning, a rule is established: it is necessary to use as many conditional sentences of different types as possible. (If clauses or conditionals) You are given 10 minutes to think about the sentence and are provided with a list of auxiliary words, phrases, and expressions.

Keywords: to survive, to escape, alone, to die, boat, signal, SOS, to try, plants, way, sea, soul, water, to grow, to search, tree(s), to be afraid of, insect, sickness, to find out, immediately, sunny, hot, however, in my opinion, to be honest, as far as I have heard, I suppose, to destroy, in my mind, quickly, in short.

Example: Independent listening practice.

Topic: Television in our lives.

Listening

For each question, there are three pictures and a short recording. Choose the correct picture and put a tick (✓) in the box below it.

1. What kind of TV programs are the most popular among teenagers?

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2. According to the speaker, at what time do we usually watch television at home?

3. What channel can give us a view of nature's life?

In conclusion, we would like to note that this method is ideal for more effective foreign language learning. Having studied the student-centered approach to teaching foreign languages to middle school students, we can draw the following conclusions:

- a student-centered approach, aimed at developing the child's individuality, will help maximize the acquisition of the foreign language material outlined in the general education program and facilitate additional self-education;

- thanks to this technology, students will be able to express themselves freely not only in their native language but also in English, thus giving a chance to the future generation to develop, which will be able to interact with the rest of humanity in a way that will ensure their thoughts and ideas are understood;

- and finally, the process of learning a foreign language will be quite interesting and will not present any particular difficulties, as teachers are always open and willing to help the child learn something new.

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